

CREATING A SOFTWARE PACKAGE FOR AUTOMATIC READING OF READER TITLE PAGES

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ABSTRACT

This article analyzes the literature on the creation of a software package for automatic reading of reader title pages.

It is important to create a software package that automatically reads title pages. Microprocessors began to be part of some automation and control tools. Digital data transfer between individual devices became the basis for building computer network management systems. The technological process control system of a new structure, which provides digital communication between certain data processing devices, is decentralized - automated control systems of technological processes or distributed - in the 70s and 80s of the XX century, the world's leading manufacturers of automation tools used software and hardware to build automated control systems of technological processes or distributed began to produce a set of tools. The main characteristics of such collections are their flexibility, the ability to operate in a single system, standardization of interfaces, and functional completeness that allows the construction of automated control systems of entire technological processes or a distributed one only from these collection tools. A set of such tools was named software-technical complexes DTM. Currently, the automation of most technological processes is carried out on the basis of universal microprocessor controller tools, the software complex of which is called DTM. Software and technical complexes consist of a set of microprocessor automation tools (microprocessor controllers, devices that establish communication with the object), operator display panels and servers performing various tasks, industrial networks, which allow connecting the listed components of controller software and operator display panels. The increase in the information power (amount of input-output variables) of the control object, the expansion of the range of issues to be solved at the higher level of control, and the increase in accuracy indicators lead to the emergence of more complex structures of software-technical complexes.

- operating systems - designed to establish communication between the computer and the user, control the work of the computer and programs. Examples: MS DOS, Windows XP,

Vista, Linux, Unix, OS/2, Mac X, etc.;

- text editor - a program that performs tasks such as text entry, editing, saving and opening, printing, text formatting. Examples: MS Word, Lexicon, Wordpad, Notepad, etc.;

- spreadsheets - a program that allows you to enter data such as text, numbers and formulas into a table, perform calculations on them, create diagrams. Examples: Lotus, MS Excel, etc.;

- database management system - a program that performs tasks such as entering and organizing data in special tables, searching for necessary information, creating a database. Examples: MS Access, Foxpro, Clipper, Paradox, Oracle, etc.;

- creating a presentation - a program that has the ability to create a demonstration and a presentation on various topics, to add tables, pictures, audio, video and multimedia information to them. Examples: MS PowerPoint, Macromedia Director;

- graphic editor - a program that performs tasks such as creation, editing, processing of raster, vector and other graphics. Examples: Adobe Photoshop, Corel Draw, Macromedia Flash, Macromedia FreeHand, Adobe Illustrator, 3D Studio Max, Maya.

- multimedia programs - this category of programs are programs that create the ability to open and play various types of multimedia information files (audio, video, etc.) and perform various other actions on them. Examples: Sound Forge, Cakewalk, WinAmp, Windows Media Player, DivX Player, etc.;

- antivirus - a program that protects and protects the computer from viruses, checks and treats hard drives and media for viruses. Examples: Norton Antivirus, NOD32, MacAfee Antivirus, Panda Antivirus, DrWeb, Antivirus Kaspersky and others;

- archiver - a program that performs tasks such as compacting data on a computer, i.e. archiving, extracting, updating. Examples: ARJ, RAR, ZIP, WinZip, WinAce, WinRAR;

- file managers - allows you to perform a number of actions on files and directories (directory, directory) - create, delete, copy, rename, move, edit, open, etc. Examples: Norton Commander, Dos Navigator, Far Manager, Volkov Commander, Total Commander, etc.

- There are also categories of games, input from scanner, reference and encyclopedia, teaching, translator and other types of programs.

Conclusion. When analyzing the literature on the creation of a software package for automatic reading of title pages, it was determined that work should be further developed in this direction.

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